

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B311
Date: 25 July 2007
Take Off 10:47:46Z
Landing: 15:14:55Z
Flight Time 4h27m09s

Campaign: COPS

Operating Area: Baden-Baden, Germany

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Al Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM 1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	University of Manchester
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics / CDP	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
7	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	VACC 1	Angela Dean	Leeds University
9	CPI 1	James Dorsey	University of Manchester
10	CPI 1	Martin Gallagher	University of Manchester
11	CVI	James Bowles	Met Office
12	Nephelometers / PSAP	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office
13	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
14	Mission Scientist 2	Hugh Coe	University of Manchester
15	Mission Scientist 3	Justin Peter	Leeds University
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Flight Track:

B311 Track 25-JUL-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B311
 Date: 25 July 2007
 Project: COPS
 Location: Baden Baden

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
093434		Start-Up	0.26 kft	147	48'46.90N, 8'05.35E
104746		T/O	1.0 kft	218	Baden Baden
105744		Videos	4.3 kft	260	Start FFC & UFC1
105854	111320	Run 1	2.5 kft	235	2.6k'
110443		JW & Nevz	2.5 kft	203	Zero cal
111427	111723	Profile 1	2.5 - 5.5 kft	075	A-B, 2.6k'-5.6k'
111838	112008	Profile 1	5.6 - 7.0 kft	107	5.6k-FL70
112009	113241	Run 2	7.0 kft	035	R2
113625	115138	Run 3	2.5 kft	233	2.6k' to A
115245	115637	Profile 2	2.5 - 7.0 kft	086	A-B, 2.6k'-FL70
115809	121047	Run 4	7.0 kft	008	B-C
121243	121531	Profile 3	7.0 - 10.0 kft	189	
121531	121913	Run 5.1	10.0 kft	216	Along ridge
121725		Event	10.0 kft	149	Over Hornisgrinde
122329	122749	Run 5.2	10.0 kft	037	Along ridge
122416		Event	10.0 kft	035	Over Hornisgrinde
123116	123636	Run 5.3	10.0 kft	236	Along ridge
123252		Videos	10.0 kft	219	Change tapes
123427		Event	10.0 kft	209	Over Hornisgrinde
123822	124407	Run 5.4	10.0 kft	035	5nm E of ridge
124010		Event	10.0 kft	017	5nm abeam Hornisgrinde
124705	125052	Run 5.5	10.0 kft	206	10nm E of ridge
125021		Event	10.5 kft	279	10nm abeam Hornisgrinde
125243	125650	Run 6.1	10.5 kft	011	5nm E of ridge
125333		Event	10.5 kft	016	5nm abeam Hornisgrinde
125836	130326	Run 6.2	10.5 kft	201	5nm E of ridge
130155		Event	10.5 kft	207	Over Hornisgrinde
130510	131000	Run 7.1	11.0 kft	035	5nm E abeam ridge
130617		Event	11.0 kft	019	5nm abeam Hornisgrinde
131148	131724	Run 7.2	11.0 kft	228	Along ridge
131520		Event	11.0 kft	210	Over Hornisgrinde
131917	132344	Run 8.1	11.5 kft	014	5nm E abeam
132054		Event	11.5 kft	018	5nm abeam Hornisgrinde
132423	132424	Run 8.1	11.5 kft	026	
132611	133137	Run 8.2	11.5 kft	221	Along ridge
132950		Event	11.5 kft	213	Over H'grinde
133302	133558	Profile 4	11.4 - 10.0 kft	063	
134156	134754	Run 9.1	10.0 kft	324	Along ridge
134456		Event	10.0 kft	295	Over Hornisgrinde
134647		Event	10.0 kft	284	Over Achern
134905	135638	Profile 5	10.0 - 3.4 kft	050	Interrupt at 3.5k'
135839	135945	Profile 5	3.4 - 2.5 kft	210	3.5-2.6k'
135945	141206	Run 10	2.5 kft	203	Baden to A, 2.6k'
140512		Videos	2.5 kft	205	Change tapes
141306	141640	Profile 6	2.5 - 7.0 kft	073	
141803	143028	Run 11	7.0 kft	014	B-C in cloud
142128		JW	7.0 kft	013	Zero cal
143219	144524	Run 12	9.5 kft	179	C-B bbove cloud
144824	145853	Run 13	7.0 kft	017	In Cloud
145102		JW	7.0 kft	007	Zero cal
150329	150833	Run 14	5.5 kft	289	Over sites,5.6k'
150408		Event	5.5 kft	292	Over Murg Valley
150631		Event	5.5 kft	295	Over Hornisgrinde
150831		Event	5.5 kft	280	Over Achern
151455		Land	0.31 kft	121	Baden Baden
151921		Shutdown	0.31 kft	152	48'46.91N, 8'05.33E

B311 Track 25-JUL-07

Scientific Aims: The goal of UK-COPS is to determine the properties of the aerosols that will likely be ingested into the convective clouds that form over the Black Forest mountains and to understand the formation and growth of ice and precipitation in these clouds. We wish to examine:

- the properties of the representative aerosol particles in the clear air that are transported into the convective clouds
- the concentration and size of cloud droplets just above cloud base
- the formation of the first ice due to primary nucleation on ice nuclei (IN)
- the development of ice via secondary processes such as the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of ice particles
- other secondary ice production processes, such as evaporative break-up;
- the production of supercooled raindrops and their role in the glaciation process
- the dependence of these processes on the dynamics of the cloud
- the production of precipitation

There will either be 2 flights per day: one in clear air to measure the properties of the aerosols and one later in the convective clouds; or the two parts will be flown in a single flight. Measurements will be made in cumulus clouds when their tops are about 0°C through to when the tops have grown to about -20°C.

Weather conditions:

Developing showers over the Black Forest mountains, Germany, within Box A and probably B.

Safety: Regions that paint RED on the aircraft weather radar should be avoided. No flight into clouds known to be producing lightning. There may be coordination with the DO-128 in Boxes A and B. The French and German Falcons may also be operating in the area.

Key instruments and their operation:

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS, INU, turbulence probe. When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe and calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics/Aerosol

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP, CIP, SID-1 and SID-2. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops ($d > 100 \mu\text{m}$) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- CPI as above
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where straight/level and in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Managers log.
- TWC - profile ascents/descents should avoid cloud if possible
- AMS -
- CVI - below cloud base, normal operation is in aerosol mode; above cloud base, normal operation is in CVI mode
- VACC - in straight and level clear-air, 10 min runs; during cloud work and profiles, single temperature.

Sortie Brief: COPS – Convective and Orographically-Induced Precipitation Study FINAL
Flight Number: B311
Date: 25 July 2007
Mission Scientists: Keith Bower and Hugh Coe
TO Time: 12:50 local
Box activated: 14-17 local
Other a/c: Possible: DO-128 (Coord with 146) and French Falcon and DLR Falson

Sortie Aims: To measure properties of aerosols in the clear air and the dev of convective clouds.

Sortie Location: Clear air in Rhine Valley and in convective clouds over B. F. mountains. Leg over supersites.

Sortie Summary:

1. Characterise properties of aerosols in clear air at low levels.
2. Penetrate cumulus clouds preferably near the top of the cloud in the updraught. All cloud penetrations should be with *wings level*. Two principal options are:
 - A. stationary cloud or system of clouds;
 - B. several cumulus clouds either in area (low wind) or passing through the area.
3. Characterise properties of aerosols in detrainment layers around cloud.
4. Overfly supersites M, H and R.

Sortie Detail:

1. Out-of-Cloud: All changes in altitude at standard rates (1000 ft/min).
2 x Rhine Valley aerosol legs (70 mins)
2. Cloud work:

Note an important feature is to ascend with tops. This requires a non-standard ascent as fast as possible. Contact DO-128 on COPS frequency. Relay cloud top info to the DO-128.

Option A: Isolated developing clouds – ascend with the clouds near their top. All penetrations at constant altitude.

- A.1 Proceed to about 0°C or top of cloud.
- A.2 Adjust altitude to about 1000 ft below cloud top and penetrate cloud. The penetration should be made at a constant azimuth and altitude if possible. It is important to penetrate the growing turret in the updraught region. A few seconds after clearing cloud, turn and ascend for return to same region of cloud as quickly as possible using procedure turn.
- A.3 Repeat A.2, ascending with the top (if appropriate) at the end of each penetration out of cloud, until FL200 or FL240, or cloud becomes too developed.
- A.4 Repeat A.1 - A.4 for a new developing cumulus, go to **Option B**, or exit box.

Option B: Many developing cumulus clouds – sample clouds at constant altitude.

- B.1 Proceed to 0°C
- B.2 Commence 10 min runs (turning where appropriate) in along shear direction. Adjust track to randomly sample the updraught regions of growing turrets.
- B.3 Ascend to -5°C (i.e. approximately 3500 ft) and repeat above for 10 min.
- B.5 Repeat for -10°C, -15°C and -20°C if possible.

3. Detrainment layers

Proceed to level where cloud is being detrained from cloud and either make penetrations or circle around the cloud.

4. Leg over supersites Murg Valley (M), Hornisgrinde (H) and Achern (R) at about 5500 ft if in clear air. (15 min). Please make SATCOM phone call to A: Stephen's mobile (0163 8064064) and B: Ops Centre (07229 66 2550, or 2551) 15 mins before overpass of Supersites.
N.B. Suggest if the UK TV cameras are at Hornisgrande, we do a banked 45 degree turn over the Hornisgrande supersite to show off the new FAAM logo on the tailfin.

Mission Scientist Debrief Summary

Flight: B311, July 25th 2007

Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Summary of the weather conditions:

There was a ridge of high pressure present over much of France and the North sea which was gradually moving eastwards during the day (predicted to be over Germany by 18:00z). There were patches of cloud present in the COPS area early in the morning which dissipated well (a couple of hours) before T/O. Winds were westerly and light (<10kts) at the surface and predicted to be 25kts/278° at 700mb and 45 kts/315° at 500mb during the flight. However, early soundings showed 2 inversions present, one at low level (which was expected to dissipate by T/O) and one at 700mb, which was expected to strengthen and limit the height of any convective clouds forming. Prior to T/O more recent (COPS) soundings showed a second inversion at 500mb.

Scientific Aims;

The flight aimed to probe the development of any convective clouds forming over the western edge of the Black Forest region (ie over the mountains to the east of the Rhine) that were predicted to develop as surface warming produced sufficient energy to overcome the inversion. Aerosol characterisation legs in the Rhine valley were also to be conducted to characterise the aerosol input into the Black Forest valleys feeding the convective clouds. Plan A was then to examine development of the ice phase as described in the default sortie brief. If the convection was insufficient to produce clouds cold enough to develop the ice phase, an alternate plan B was to examine the processing of the aerosol through the warm convective clouds by measuring the aerosol outflow from these cloud systems. Finally, if no clouds were to form over the mountains, the objectives of alternate plan C were to examine the structures of any “dry convection” occurring over the mountains.

Points defined:

Point EDSB (48 46' 8"N, 8 4' 8"E) Karlsruhe/Baden-Baden; Point A (48 05'N, 7 38'E); Point B (48 2'N, 8 6'E); Point C (48 51'N, 8 27'E) for aerosol legs; predefined boxes A and B (between FL100 and FL200) - activated between 1200Z and 1500z.

Summary of the flight:

Initially, the low level leg over the central Rhine Valley between EDSB and Point A was conducted at 2600ft. As per the previous flight, the aerosol concentrations (CN) and NO_x levels were highest in a broad plume towards the northern end of this leg (see figure 1 – CN and NO_x during Run 1), peaking at 4000-5000 cm⁻³ and 5-6 ppbv respectively. During the profile ascent from A to B the bases of clouds were seen to be around 5000ft so it was necessary to carry out the leg B to C northwards above the Black Forest mountains at 7000ft. At this time cloud tops were estimated to be 7500-8000ft (NB during the ascent out of Baden-Baden airport in the middle of the valley the bases of the broken cumulus were seen at around 3500ft). A similar CN and NO_x concentration structure was seen along the leg B-C although the higher concentrations at the northern end of the leg were lower than during R1. Cloud Physics PCASP concentrations were peaking at around 300 cm⁻³ (a more realistic value than on B310 following cleaning and realignment of the probe). Nephelometer measurements

showed similar patterns to the NO_x and CN data around the circuit. The Rhine valley legs were repeated a second time. On the EDSB –A leg (R3), PCASP peaked at around 700cm⁻³. On the second B-C leg (R4) at 7000ft the aircraft flew in cloud free air and through a number of turrets (see photos). The AMS had noise problems during all of these Rhine Valley – Black Forest “aerosol” legs, and was only improved following a series of corrective measures (including rebooting logging system and mass spectrometer) on later upper level legs.

Figure 1: Screen dump views of CN and NO_x measurements during Run 1 (11:58:53-11:13:19) from north to south along the EDSB to A leg at 2600ft

A profile ascent (P3) was carried out up to FL100 to enter the base of the cloud boxes A and B. Unfortunately this level was above the tops of any convective turrets and so a version of Option C was carried out, whereby a series of legs were carried out along the western edge of box A in a N-S and S-N orientation above the Black Forest mountains at 10,000ft (in order to test out the “Dry convection” or “Gadian” hypothesis). It was not possible to determine the presence of “dry convection” regions from the onboard data, and the strong suspicion was that at FL100 we were too high above the dry lid and inversion capping the convection (and cloud tops) to see this effect. Never-the-less, a series of legs were carried out over the box edge and then on parallel tracks 5 and 10 files further east, in case any such signals could be picked up in post flight analysis (the legs 5 miles east of the box edge were more or less over the north end of the aerosol legs B-C). Finally, legs over the box edge (and 5 miles east) were then carried out at altitudes of 500 and 1000ft higher than the starting FL100 legs. As there were no signs of convection being strong enough to enable cloud formation in the box at any time in the near future (see tephigram from the end of the mission below – highlighting the inversion and dry layer above 700mbar) it was

decided to leave the boxes A-B and carry out further aerosol (and cloud legs) around the aerosol circuit. This was to enable measurements with a now working AMS to be made at low level in the Rhine valley (R10 at 2600ft) to characterise the aerosol input to the system (and for comparison of this days aerosol with measurements of valley aerosol on subsequent flights), and to make measurements within the cloud over the Black Forest mountains (Runs 11 and 13) and just above these cloud tops (Run 12 at 9500ft). The mission was completed by carrying out a run (R13) overpassing the supersites at 5500ft (east to west) before returning to base.

Figure 2:
 Tephigram of all the data from flight B311, showing inversion and dry layer at 700mb, preventing convection and cloud formation at higher levels.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B-311... Date 25/07/09 Name MSC1 K.N BOWER Page 1 of 5

Time (Z)	Run	Altitude (ft)	Wind direction/speed °/kts	Position	Comments
12:35	(KNS local)				Engine Start
12:43	(" ")				Taxi
12:48:10	(" ")				260°/10 kts T/O (1015)
	Climb	3500'			CB - small stuff - broken clouds
	Transit	6000'			CT - near this altitude (but some stuff above at 7000-8000ft)
10:56:41	Descent				Descending to start of aerosol leg.
10:55:53	R1(S)	2600'		45°48'/8°6'E	Start of 1 st Aerosol leg N→S NB Core Chem missed start of run for cal - will do cal during last 3 mins of run.
11:13:19	R1(E)	2600'	69°/3 m/s	45°0'/7°36'E	T/Td 15.44/10.62 Hwd/S 175°/228 kts
11:14:25	P1(S)	2600→5600'			Start of profile 1
11:17:22	P1(E)				Just in cloud base - traffic so ascending
11:18:29	Climb to 7000'				(P1 recommence) Climbing to 7000' to avoid traffic
11:20:08	P1(E)/R2(S)	7000'			Broken clouds, CT's ~ 7500ft PCASP 1000/cm ³ Cloud Phys PCASP 300 cm ³ Zero of 2D probes
11:22:10	R2	7000			Into cloud 782 mb 3.83°/1.61° 4 m/s / 225° 24 kts / 10° heading
11:24:08	R2	7000			VACC screwed so switched off.
11:27:26	R2	7000			Cloud (short transit)
11:28:15	R2	7000			Cloud
11:28:26	R2	7000			Out of cloud
11:29:29	R2	7000	48		Cloud - great one! Marked pos in GPS for later. Velocity at 48.3°N more intense than 48.75°N last pass - more active to S
11:32:40	R2(E)	7000	10 m/s / 253°	45°46'/8°24'E	781 mb 3.95°/-5.73°C 22°/231 kts

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 311 Date 25/6/07 Name MSC1 KN BOWEN Page 2 of 5

Time (Z)	Run	Altitude (ft)	Wind direction/speed °/kts	Position	Comments
					PCASP: 200 @ N end aerosol run
					300 @ S end of run
					Neph - same as CPC - higher N end of Aerosol box
11:36:24	R3(S)	2600'	3 m/s / 291°	48°48'/8°12'	NO _x higher > 2x 925 mb
11:39:00	R3	2600'			AMS O ₂ ~ 1 (mg/m ³ NO ₂) NO ₂ ~ 1.1 SO ₂ ~ 0.4 NH ₄ ~ 2.1 O ₃ < ~ 0.7 O ₃ > ~ 0.12
11:40:50					NO _x steadily increasing 4.5 parts per Cloud Phys PCASP ~ 700
					48.5N - 48.9N constant conc'n S of here
* PHOTO	11:46ish				BLIMP low due left of us - dipping into valley
11:47:50	R3	2600'	3 m/s / 254°	48°12'/7.42°E	925 mb 208° 221 Å
11:51:36	R3(E)		4 m/s / 116°		NO _x doubling again 15.54°C / 10.71°C
11:52:43	P2	2500 → 7000'			
		4800'			CB Broken / Scattered.
11:56:35	P2 (E)	7000'	6 m/s / 252°	48°00'/8°0'E	780 mb 4.15°C / 0.54°C
11:57:40					Patch of Cloud - still turning
11:58:08	R4 (S)	7000'	4 m/s / 213°		B → C (S → N) 780 mb. 4.08° / 2.13°
11:58:35	R4				
* PHOTO	12:01:30ish				Cloud targets ahead.
12:02:24	R4	7000'			Cloud, NO _x rising CT ~ highest about 7500 ft.
+ PHOTO'S	12:04:20ish				Pies
12:05:17	R4	7000			Cloud. NO _x rising
12:08:00					NO _x peak falling
12:10:46	R4 (E)	7000			turning 781 mb 4.11°C / -0.97°C
					PCASP
12:12:44	P3 (S)	7000 → FL100			N → S

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 311 Date 25/07/07 Name MSC1 KN SOWER Page 3 of 5

Time (Z)	Run	Altitude (ft)	Wind direction/speed °/kts	Position	Comments
12:15:24	P3(E)	RS(S) FL100	7mb/303°	48°42'/8°18'E	Still N→S 697mb 3.65°/-36.95°C (VERY DRY AREA)
12:17:27	RS	FL100			Over Hornsgrinde - outback M. PRODS (NB Well inside E leg of airmass current run) (see screenshots file).
12:19:18	RS.1(E)	FL100			
12:23:14	RS.2(S)	FL100			S→N Flying up W edge of "Box"
12:24:14	RS.2	FL100	6mb/296°	48°30'/8°6'E	Over "M" 3.56°/-27.87°C 696mb.
(12:27:49)	RS.2(E)	FL100			(with return of FL100 and then step out E)
12:31:16	RS.3(S)	FL100			N→S
12:34:28	RS.3	FL100	7mb/308°	48°36'/8°12'E	Over "M". AMS - sensible N ₂ (209° ASMs) 3.85°/-35.08°C 696mb
12:36:36	RS.3(E)	FL100			Really dry - no chance of cloud penetrations - Flying Man Gordon request/scenario
12:38:22	RS.4(S)	FL100			Smiles to east S→N
12:40:08	RS.4	FL100			Beam "M"
12:44:07	RS.4(E)	FL100			Will move out another 5 miles to east
12:46:10	BSS(S)	FL100	9mb/296°	48°42'/8°36'E	Smiles further east N→S 696mb 3.8°C/-22.23°C Heading/Speed 204°/242kts
12:50:57	RSS(E)	FL100	5mb/295°	48°24'/8°24'E	3.53°C/-30.82°C 210°/250kts 696mb
12					Climbing to FL105 - return 5 miles to W
12:52:43	R6.1(S)	FL105			S→N Run 683mb Still too dry (5 miles E of W box edge).
12:53:32	R6.1	FL105			Beam to "M"
12:56:49	R6.1(E)	FL105	6mb/282°	48°42'/8°24'E	683mb 3.11°C/-21.85°C 17°/244kts. (Bottom (check below))
12:58:35	R6.2(S)	FL105	6mb/288°	48°42'/8°18'E	Over W edge of box. 682mb 3.48°/-21.92°
13:01:53	R6.2	FL105	5mb/291°	48°36'/8°12'E	Over "M" 683mb 3.11°/-20.98°C
13:03:34	R6.2(E)	FL105		48°30'/8°6'E	Climbing to FL110 683mb 3.03°/-19.96°C
13:05:09	R7.1(S)	FL110			Smiles out (E) of W edge of box
13:06:14	R7.1	FL110	4mb/257°	48°30'/8°18'E	Beam to "M" 670mb 2.37°/-27.28°

Mission Scientist's Log

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Time (Z)	Run	Altitude (ft)	Wind direction/speed °/kts	Position	Comments
13:09:59	R7.1(E)	FL110			
13:11:47	R7.2(S)	FL110			Run (N→S) over Wedge of Br
13:17:24	R7.2(E)	FL110			
13:19:16	R8.1(S)	FL115			Run (S→N) 650mb Veg dry.
13:24:23	R8.1(E)	FL115	5mb/273°	48°42'/8°24'E	2.53°/-27.62°C 657mb
13:26:12	R8.2(S)	FL115	6mb/290	48°46'/8°18'E	Run (N→S) 656mb 2.36°/-31.29°
13:29:44	R8.2	FL115	6mb/274°	48°36'/8°12'E	Over "H" 656mb 1.99°/-30.08° 215°/254kts.
13:31:35	R8.2(E)	FL115	4mb/268°	48°24'/8°6'E	End - will probe down to FL100
13:32:55	P4(S)	FL115-FL100		48°24'/8°12'E	Probing down.
13:35:57	P4(E)	FL100		48°30'/8°24'	E→W to cross over "H" next. 4.03°/-31.06° 695kts
13:41:54	R9.1	FL100			over "H"
					Computer monitor (pad) going mad - Reboot pc
					Over Achem.
13:50:03	PS	FL100 ↓			
	PS	5800'			Cloud Base.
13:56:35	PS(int)	3500		48°46'/8°12'E	Interrupt Probe Descent. 893mb 12.85°/6.53°C
13:55:38	PS(rec)	3500 ↓ → 2600'	6mb/291°	48°42'/8°0'E	Recommence. 894mb 13.16°/6.76°C
13:59:44	PS(E)	2600'			Start of Run
14:12:09	R10(E)	2600'			End of aerial Run - N→S Pinnac Valley.
14:13:02	P6(S)	2600 → 7000'			PCASP
14:16:39	P6(E)	FL070	4mb/243°	48°0'/8°0'E	761mb 4.7°C/6.72°C 135°/238kts.
14:18:01	R11(S)	FL070			Broken Cloud
14:21:30	R11	7000'			Photos
14:26:12	R11	7000'			Photos of "H" through cloud
14:30:27	R11(E)	7000'	5mb/235°	48°46'/8°24'	761mb 3.89°/2.63°C - climbing to FL095
14:32:18	R12(S)	9500'	3mb/298°	48°48'/8°15'	706mb 4.71°/-31.84° N→S above cloud.
14:45:22	R12(E)	9500'	4mb/269°	48°0'/8°0'E	710mb 5.15°/-31.95 Above Cloud

Mission Scientist's Log

MISSION 2

Flight No B.311

Date 25/7/07

Name HUGH COE

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Time (Z)	Run	Altitude (ft)	Wind direction/speed °/kts	Position	Comments
11:14:27	PROF1	2600-5800 ft		48.0N 47.7E	
11:17:23	PROF1	5600 ft			profile end Now at S end of Black Forest end.
					end, cat make SUR at 5600ft so continue
11:18:38	PROF1	5600		Hdg 75°	profile 1 to 7000 ft.
11:20:08	PROF1	7000 ft			profile 1 end.
11:20:09	RUN1				Start at 700
					Cloud Physics 300 p/cc CPC ~ 600-800 p/cc So in agreement.
					↳ see note at 48.3N and close to end of run 48.8N
11:24:00					HMS has some problems file writing appears to be giving zeros but numbers a part parcel are OK.
11:36:25	RUN 3	2600 ft	1 m/s 230°	48.0N	S band legs in Rhine to part A. at 2600 ft
11:52:45	END R3 START R2	2600 ft			Cloud base 4500 ft
11:56:37	END R2 P2	7000 ft	9 m/s 240° T 4°C Td 2.1°C.		End profile
12:06					The pollution plume at the N end of the Rhine Valley and Black Forest legs is consistent for all runs The cloud is Cu, scattered base at 4000 ft; top at 7500-8000 ft.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 311 Date 25/7/07 Name NUGM CCE Mission 2 Page 5 of 5

Time (Z)	Run	Altitude (ft)	Wind direction/speed °/kts	Position	Comments
14:12:06	R10	2600 ft			end of run 10
	START P6	→ 7000 ft			
14:16:40	END P6	7000 ft			Start
					Start of northward run up the Rhine Valley.
14:18:03	START R11	7100 ft			
14:29					Fine aerosol in the cloudy Cu layer at 7000'. The Cu are separated and there are clear gaps but are at time intervals
					Updrafts/downdrafts ± 1 m/s
					Nephelometer scattering.
					30 m ⁻¹ (blue)
14:30:28	END R11	F1070			All fine aerosol (No CIVI pump cores only)
		F1095			end of run ascending to F1095
14:41					No aerosol at F1090
					v clear PCASP 30 p/lcc
					neph 0-3 m ⁻¹ no variability
					no aerosol getting to this height
					In lower layers wet neph sees some growth; more than on prev days consistent with AMS seeing more inorganic to organic than previously.

14:45:24 END R12
 14:58:53 END R13
 15:03:29 R14 over supersonic
 M 15:03:45
 H 15:06:48
 A 15:08:33
 Descending into cloud at 7500'
 Touch down @ 15:15:10

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B311

Date: 25/07/07	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 10:08:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
10:56:00	185	0.08	168	1	10	0		0								FFSSP base increased. 2DC reset	
10:57:45	572	0.08	199	5	1	0		0								FL040	
10:58:27	909	0.08	199	10	0	0		0								FL030	
10:58:57	788	0.09	199	8	1	0		0								START RUN 1 @ FL026	
11:00:00	1157	0.08	199	8	1	0		0									
11:02:00	1397	0.08	199	8	2	0		0									
11:04:00	870	0.08	199	10	1	0		0									
11:06:00	799	0.09	199	6	1	0		0									
11:09:00	591	0.08	200	8	0	0		0									
11:10:00	549	0.09	200	6	0	0		0									
11:12:00	544	0.09	200	2	0	0		0									
11:13:21	573	0.09	200	8	1	0		0								END RUN1 @ FL026	
11:15:00	633	0.09	200	8	1	0		0								FL030	
11:16:00	542	0.09	200	8	1	0		0								FL040	
11:16:53	385	0.08	200	8	1	0		0								FL050	
11:17:25	293	0.08	200	10	20	0		0								END PROFILE 1 @ FL054	
11:19:00	182	0.08	303	5	0	0		0								FL060	
11:20:07	287	0.08	376	5000	5000	0		0								FL070 END PROFILE START RUN	
11:22:35	261	0.09	495	5	200	0		500	800							FFSSP SYNCH'ED	
11:24:00	310	0.09	495	8	1	0		0									
11:26:00	236	0.08	495	7	0	0		0									
11:27:42	405	0.09	560	5000	8000	0		1000	800							CLOUD	
11:30:00	481	0.09	622	5000	3000	0		1000	800								
11:32:00	368	0.09	622	10	200	0		0									
11:32:42	206	0.08	622	2	0	0		0								END RUN FL070	
11:34:41	579	0.08	622	7	0	0		0								FL050	
11:35:10	697	0.09	622	10	1	0		0								FL040	
11:35:54	867	0.09	622	7	1	0		0								FL030	
11:36:33	834	0.09	622	10	1	0		0								START RUN B-A	
11:38:00	1066	0.09	623	10	2	0		0									
11:40:00	991	0.09	623	8	1	0		0									
11:42:00	779	0.08	623	8	0	0		0									
11:44:00	656	0.09	623	8	1	0		0									
11:46:00	872	0.09	623	8	1	0		0								SID2 RESTARTED FILE B311C	
11:48:00	635	0.09	623	2	1	0		0									
11:50:00	622	0.09	623	2	2	0		0									
11:51:39	722	0.09	623	8	1	0		0								END RUN 3 @ FL026	
11:53:15	552	0.09	624	20	1	0		0								FL030	
11:54:09	471	0.08	624	10	1	0		0								FL040	
11:55:00	421	0.09	624	5	0	0		0								FL050	
11:55:47	332	0.09	624	8	1	0		0								FL060	
11:56:38	337	0.08	624	2	0	0		0								FL070	
11:58:00	306	0.08	640	0	1	0		0									
11:59:44	408	0.09	705	30	2000	0		100								CLOUD	
12:00:00	409	0.09	706	7	2	0		0									
12:02:00	402	0.08	706	7	10	0		0									

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B311

Date: 25/07/07	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 10:08:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:02:49	480	0.09	754	5000	2000	0		100								CLOUD	
12:04:00	335	0.09	754	5	1	0		0									
12:05:40	601	0.24	796	3000	1000	0		400	1000							FFSSP SYNCH'ED	
12:08:00	530	0.09	852	8	1	0		0									
12:10:00	352	0.09	866	2	1	0		0								FFSSP SYNCH'ED	
12:10:49	397	0.09	866	4	2	0		0								END RUN	
12:12:00	70	0.08	866	2	20	0		0									
12:13:44	32	0.07	866	0	0	0		0								FL080	
12:14:35	13	0.07	866	0	0	0		0								FL090	
12:15:30	14	0.09	866	0	20	0		0								FL100 END PROFILE START RUN	
12:18:00	20	0.09	866	0	0	0		0								SID2 RESTARTED B311D	
12:20:00	34	0.09	866	1	0	0		0								SID2 RESTARTED B311E	
12:25:00	22	0.07	866	0	10	0		0								SID2 " STOPPED RESPONDING"	
12:30:00	25	0.08	866	0	0	0		0									
12:35:00	22	0.08	867	1	0	0		0								OVER HORNISGRINDE	
12:40:00	21	0.08	867	0	0	0		0								SOME SID2 SIGNALS SINCE LAST LOG	
12:45:00	28	0.08	867	0	0	0		0									
12:50:00	24	0.08	867	0	0	0		0									
12:51:39	18	0.08	867	0	0	0		0								FL105	
12:55:00	20	0.08	867	0	0	0		0								FL105	
13:00:00	20	0.08	867	1	0	0		0								FL105	
13:04:17	20	0.09	867	1	0	0		0								FL110	
13:10:00	15	0.08	867	0	0	0		0								FL110 END OF RUN 7	
13:15:00	35	0.07	868	0	0	0		0								FL110	
13:18:16	17	0.07	868	0	0	0		0								FL115	
13:20:00	21	0.09	868	0	8	0		0								RUN 8.1	
13:24:24	46	0.08	868	0	0	0		0								END RUN 8.1 more variable PCASP at FL115	
13:26:11	29	0.08	868	0	0	0		0								Start RUN 8.2	
13:30:00	18	0.07	868	1	0	0		0								OVER HORNISGRINDE	
13:34:10	26	0.08	868	0	0	0		0								FL110	
13:35:50	21	0.07	868	0	0	0		0								FL100 END PROFILE	
13:40:00	30	0.08	868	0	10	0		0									
13:45:00	23	0.08	868	0	10	0		0									
13:50:20	14	0.08	869	0	0	0		0								FL090	
13:51:30	20	0.07	869	0	0	0		0								FL080	
13:52:36	678	0.09	869	500	100	0		0								FL070	
13:53:45	705	0.09	996	300	80	0		700	800							FL060 FFSSP SYNCH'ED	
13:54:48	597	0.09	998	8	1	0		0								FL050	
13:55:51	598	0.08	998	5	1	0		0								FL040	
13:59:12	677	0.08	999	7	1	0		0								FL030	
13:59:44	799	0.08	1002	8	2	0		0								FL026 START RUN	
14:03:00	881	0.08	3328	8	1	0		0								FFSSP SYNCH'ED3 TIMES . DATA OUT.	
14:05:00	606	0.08	3328	10	2	0		0									
14:07:00	603	0.09	3328	10	1	0		0									
14:09:00	614	0.08	3329	5	1	0		0									
14:11:00	580	0.08	3329	8	1	0		0									

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Date: 25/07/07	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 10:08:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 3
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
14:12:09	561	0.08	3329	5	1	0		0								END RUN 10 @ FL026	
14:13:08	657	0.09	3329	5	0	0		0								START PROFILE FL026	
14:13:35	476	0.09	3329	8	1	0		0								FL030	
14:14:12	420	0.08	3329	5	1	0		0								FL040	
14:14:57	344	0.08	3329	5	1	0		0								FL050	
14:16:04	333	0.08	3350	5	1	0		0								FL065	
14:16:40	422	0.08	3702	5000	8000	0		500	1000							FL070	
14:18:00	342	0.09	3702	2	1	0		0								START RUN 11	
14:19:00	315	0.24	4023	5000	8000	0		400	1000							CLOUD	
14:20:00	428	0.09	4032	2	1	0		0									
14:22:00	423	0.09	4049	2	1	0		0									
14:23:35	436	0.10	4100	3000	5000	0		100									
14:25:00	418	0.09	4156	10	1	0		0									
14:26:08	365	0.12	4262	5000	5000	0		200	1200								
14:27:16	265	0.11	4451	5000	8000	0		400	1200								
14:28:00	737	0.15	4627	5000	8000	0		600	1000								
14:29:05	545	0.09	4697	5000	5000	0		500	1200								
14:30:29	452	0.09	4706	8	1	0		100	800							END RUN 11	
14:31:16	24	0.09	4706	0	0	0		0								FL080	
14:31:42	15	0.08	4706	0	100	0		0								FL090	
14:32:20	22	0.08	4706	0	0	0		0								FL095	
14:35:00	23	0.09	4706	0	0	0		0									
14:40:00	25	0.09	4707	0	0	0		0								FFSSP base signal increased	
14:45:00	17	0.08	4707	0	0	0		0									
14:45:25	24	0.08	4707	0	0	0		0								End run	
14:46:01	92	0.08	4707	2	0	0		0								FL090	
14:46:55	333	0.09	4707	2	0	0		0								FL080	
14:47:46	337	0.09	4707	2	1	0		0								FL070	
14:48:24	443	0.09	4707	8	1	0		0								START RUN	
14:49:37	244	0.14	4839	5000	8000	0		50									
14:51:00	467	0.09	4883	1000	2000	0		0								FFSSP SYNCH'ED	
14:51:50	546	0.15	4911	5000	5000	0		100									
14:53:30	277	0.26	5071	8000	10000	0		375	1000								
14:54:25	506	0.012	5187	1000	300	0		150	1000								
14:55:18	664	0.30	5403	8000	8000	0		400	1000								
14:56:00	213	0.30	5524	5000	8000	0		150	1000							FFSSP SYNCH'ED	
14:58:00	542	0.09	5646	8	1	0		0									
14:58:56	569	0.10	5677	4000	8000	0		100								END RUN	
14:59:54	807	0.09	5692	10	8	0		0								FL060	
15:01:50	559	0.09	5692	5	1	0		0								FL055	
15:03:28	566	0.09	5692	5	1	0		0								START RUN @ FL055	
15:05:00	581	0.08	5692	2	0	0		0									
15:07:00	618	0.09	5692	5	0	0		0									
15:08:36	543	0.09	5692	2	1	0		0								END RUN/SCIENCE	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B311 **T/O:** 10:47:46
Date of flight: 25/07/07 **Land:** 15:14:55

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		To Exeter
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B311
Date of Flight: 25/07/07

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	11724 blocks
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 118692
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 34464 Blocks written = 34464 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 104000 End = 152000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size?
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images No 2DC images Noise on 2DP Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 104500 End = 151500 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = b311_tas</p> <p>Start = 104500 End = 151500</p> <p>Time data processed to = 145604 2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>No M5 created!!</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records = 31, 178</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>		<p>Correlated?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B311
Date of Flight: 25/07/07

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 1.0 104800 151400
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = _tas Y = X+1 = _tas_pcasp
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Data present in _tas_pcasp Merged OK?

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.311**.....

 Date **25/07/07**.....

 Operator's name: **D. Tiddeman**.....

 Page **1** of **1**.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
105300	—	—	12.5	35	47	10	25	Humidifier on On
10 110130	Run 1	2600	14.5	50	41.3	30	10.5	
110520	"	"	14.4	50	59.1	40	30	
111240	"	"	14.4	50.7	78.3	10°	40	
112255	Run 2	7000	12.7	30.1	37.4	40	13.5	
112923	"	"	12.5	28.8	72.1	45°	40°	
113210	"	"	12.4	22.6	83.9	10°	45°	
114025	Run 3	2500	14.5	51.0	54.0	45°	15	
114635	"	"	14.4	52.0	90.5	10°	45°	
115918	Run 4	7000	12.5	27.5	39.5	45°	11.5°	
120754	"	"	12.5	27.5	87.0	10°	45°	
121648	Run 5	10000	11.4	0.8	34.1	10	16.5	Humidifier Off
134908	Prot 5	"	11.0	0.0	29.5	10	19°	Humidifier On
13520	Prot 5	4000	13.6	40.3	34.5	40	10°	
135716		3500	14.0	45.1	50.2	10	25°	
14:00:40	Run 10	2600	14.4	49.4	47.7	40	16°	
14:04:54	"	"	14.4	58.2	83.5	45	40°	
140808	"	"	14.4	60.8	91.2	10	45°	
141830	Run 11	7000	12.5	37.6	46.1	45	16.5	
142440	"	"	12.4	37.0	89.7	10	45°	
143355	Run 12	9500	11.5	4.1	43.8		15°	Humidifier Off

B311 CVI log

7/25/07 10:53:48 AM
7/25/07 10:53:55 AM
7/25/07 10:54:02 AM
7/25/07 10:59:00 AM r1 2600ft clear
7/25/07 11:11:44 AM
7/25/07 11:13:26 AM
7/25/07 11:13:39 AM eor1 clear
7/25/07 11:18:01 AM 5600ft level, some clouds
7/25/07 11:20:11 AM r2 @7000ft
7/25/07 11:20:28 AM intermittent cu
7/25/07 11:28:06 AM still patchy cloud though above most of it
7/25/07 11:32:43 AM eor2
7/25/07 11:36:37 AM r3 2600ft
7/25/07 11:43:38 AM cloud physics pcase about half cvi values??
7/25/07 11:51:36 AM eor3 clear
7/25/07 11:58:08 AM r4 @7000ft occasional cloud tops/clouds
7/25/07 12:02:29 PM cloud
7/25/07 12:05:28 PM cloud
7/25/07 12:06:44 PM cloud
7/25/07 12:10:52 PM eor4
7/25/07 12:13:15 PM p3 to 10000ft
7/25/07 12:19:06 PM cloud physics pcase about 25 compared to CVI 100
7/25/07 12:19:19 PM eor 5
7/25/07 12:19:34 PM clear air
7/25/07 12:23:45 PM cnc much larger than ultra fine. 670 vs 250c/cc
7/25/07 12:24:42 PM r6 started about 3min ago....
7/25/07 12:31:27 PM r5.3 10000ft
7/25/07 12:37:01 PM eor5.3
7/25/07 12:38:42 PM r5.4 10000ft clear air
7/25/07 12:44:18 PM eor5.4
7/25/07 12:46:25 PM r5.5
7/25/07 12:51:20 PM eor5.5 & profile to 10500ft
7/25/07 12:52:15 PM
7/25/07 12:53:07 PM r6.1 @ 10500ft
7/25/07 12:56:55 PM eor6.1
7/25/07 12:58:46 PM r6.2
7/25/07 1:05:28 PM r7.1 @ 11000ft
7/25/07 1:05:41 PM clear air above clouds
7/25/07 1:34:02 PM p4 decent
7/25/07 1:42:20 PM r9.1 10000ft clear
7/25/07 1:48:03 PM eor9.1
7/25/07 1:49:32 PM profile to 6000ft
7/25/07 1:53:49 PM cloud??
7/25/07 1:54:55 PM PCASP huge noisy counts on profile down
7/25/07 1:55:51 PM
7/25/07 1:56:03 PM
7/25/07 1:58:54 PM PCASP power cycled
7/25/07 2:01:27 PM no change after power cycle
7/25/07 2:01:57 PM run at 2500ft down valley
7/25/07 2:02:48 PM power cycled again
7/25/07 2:09:56 PM clear and below cloud
7/25/07 2:12:18 PM eor10
7/25/07 2:13:31 PM PCASP sample reduced to zero, bins 2+3 maxed out all others next
to zero
7/25/07 2:14:53 PM profile up, + reasonable pcase data when flow put back on!
7/25/07 2:15:15 PM cvi mode to catch clouds.
7/25/07 2:16:56 PM cloud
7/25/07 2:18:19 PM flow adjusted
7/25/07 2:18:53 PM cloud
7/25/07 2:20:34 PM cloud
7/25/07 2:22:19 PM CVI mode not zeroing between clouds
7/25/07 2:23:12 PM Attempt to set L value, slider has little effect. left at 2.8
7/25/07 2:30:35 PM eor 11

Flight:

B311

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 20/08/2007
17:28:27

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

01/08/2007 12:59:45

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B311

Date: 25/07/2007

Instruments

1. AMS – writing data to files but not transferring to hard disk. Problems with inorganics.
2. VACC – not working after t/o. Switch off.
3. Mission Scientist's laptop cursor went haywire. Rebooted pc then okay.

Aircraft

1. Aircraft hit 2 birds on take-off

Satcom-H Calls

Hornisgrinde

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 25/07/07

Flight No: B311

Pre-Flighter: BW

No.	<input type="checkbox"/> or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	Dry
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nezvorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	Dry
16	<input type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	Dry
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	No zero cal
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	CPI seat
Proceed to External Checks				
External Checks overleaf →				

Pre-Flighter's Log

No.	√ or x	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	<i>No camera</i>
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input type="checkbox"/>	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input type="checkbox"/>	All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/>	Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/>	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				Signed
43	<input type="checkbox"/>	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	<input type="checkbox"/>	ICEX applied		
45	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		<i>a)Nil b)1-2 drops c)1/4 full or more</i>
46	<input type="checkbox"/>	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B311:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
VACC	VACC operator does not create a log sheet
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
CPI	CPI operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	02 Oct 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1	15 Jan 2008	Doug Anderson	Updated video tape holder information
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Upward Facing Cameras
2 x Forward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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